

Abazitabira bose bazatoranywa begerewe n’umwe mu bagize itsinda ry’ubushakashatsi ahantu rusange, maze ubushakashatsi busobanurwe mu magambo hakoreshejwe iyi nyandiko ikurikira:

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Mwaramutse / Mwiriwe. Nitwa “[izina]”, ndi umushakashatsi wa [Izina ryikigo], nkaba ndi gukora ku mushinga w’ubushakashatsi witwa “Kunoza Imigaragarire y’Ibyemezo byo Kwemeza Kwishyura kuri MoMo.”

Umenyereye Mobile Money (MoMo), uburyo bwo kohereza cg kwakira amafaranga kuri telephone?

[Niba aro yego], Ukoresha MoMo Wohereza cg wakira amafaranga (mugihe Wishyura cg Wishyurwa)?

Uyu mushinga ugamije kumenya uko Abanyarwanda bakoresha MoMo, hagamijwe guteza imbere uburyo bwizewe kandi bubika ibanga.

Ese waba witeguye kwitabira ikiganiro kuri iyi ngingo kizamara hagati y’iminota 60? Ushobora kugikora nonaha cyangwa tukagishakira indi saha ikunogeye. Uzahabwa amafaranga 7,500 RWF anyuzwa kuri MoMo nk’ishimwe ryo kwitabira. Ubushakashatsi buzagusaba gusubiza ibibazo bijyanye n’uburyo ukoresha MoMo, uko wemeza ko wishyuye neza kuri MoMo, ndetse n’amakuru amwe y’ibanze akwerekereyeho.

- Ese hari ikibazo ufite ku bijyanye n’ubu bushakashatsi?
- Ese ufite imyaka 18 cyangwa urayirengeje?
- Ese umaze nibura imyaka 5 utuye mu Rwanda?
- Waba wifuza kwitabira ubu bushakashatsi?
- *[Niba ubyemeye]* Ni byiza cyane! Waba wifuza kukuzura nonaha cyangwa nyuma? Twifuza ko byakorwa nonaha, ariko nyuma nabyo birashoboka.
- *[Niba ari nyuma]* Ni ryari byakubereye gukora ikiganiro? Waba ushaka ko tugikora dukoresheje WhatsApp cyangwa duhura imbonankubone?

*[Waba ugiye gukora ubushakashatsi nonaha cyangwa nyuma, tubanza gusaba uburenganzira bwawe mu buryo bwanditse.]*

Mbere y’uko dukomeza, turagusaba gusoma no kuzura urupapuro rw’ubwememererwe.

*[tegereza igihe uwo mubaza asoma kandi asinya urupapuro rw’ubwememererwe.]*

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